

ONLINE LEARNING AND EMOTIONAL PRESENCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Available Online: August 2023
Revised: June 2023
Accepted: June 2023
Received: July 2022

Volume I Issue 3 (2023)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10022860
E-ISSN: 2984-7184
P-ISSN: 2984-7176
<https://getinternational.org/research/>

Abstract:

This study delved into the realm of emotional presence and its potential impact on students' academic performance within collaborative online learning environments. While emotions were recognized as influential factors in the learning process, the specific relationship between emotional presence and cognitive outcomes remained elusive, particularly in the context of virtual classrooms. This research addressed a critical gap by investigating the relationships between emotional presence and students' academic achievements in online classes. An exploratory sequential mixed-methods approach incorporating both quantitative and qualitative components was used. Fifty (50) senior high school students engaged in online learning were selected through the purposive sampling technique. Quantitative findings revealed that emotions did not exhibit a significant correlation with students' academic achievements in the online learning environment. However, insights from the qualitative analysis shed light on the emotional experiences of students, indicating negative emotions such as anxiety, fear, and disappointment. Despite these challenging emotions, students were still capable of achieving favorable academic outcomes. In conclusion, while the emotional presence of students may have been predominantly negative, their academic achievements in online learning environments remained satisfactory. This suggested that learners could effectively navigate and succeed within the virtual classroom setting, even in the face of emotional challenges. Educators were encouraged to create supportive online learning environments that highly addressed students' emotional needs alongside their educational requirements. By fostering emotional well-being, teachers could enhance the overall learning experience and promote positive outcomes in virtual education.

Keywords: *Emotions, Emotional Presence, Academic Achievements, Online Learning*

Recommended Citation:

Mangarin, J. (2023). ONLINE LEARNING AND EMOTIONAL PRESENCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS. GUILD OF EDUCATORS IN TESOL INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL, 1(3), 66-77. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10022860>

Introduction:

Emotion is a complicated reaction pattern that shows how people will respond to an issue or circumstance that has personal significance for them, involving experiential, behavioral, and physiological factors (American Psychological Association). Additionally, emotions are essential components of psychological makeup and play significant roles in people's lives. It sometimes determines an individual's behavioral patterns in diverse settings. It was also noticed that emotions are closely connected and have a big effect on how a person thinks and acts (Apostolidis & Tsiatsos, 2018).

Since emotion modifies every part of cognition, emotional experience is pervasive in nature and essential in academic settings. In terms of education, Bowlby (1969) said that emotions are connected to the levels of a person's intuitive assessments and evaluations of either their own organismal conditions and impulses to respond or the sequence of external conditions in which they find themselves. Some contend that emotions are important to the human experience and that it is crucial to consider people's responses to both internal and external events (LeDoux et al., 1996; Plutchick et al., 2003; Turner & Stets, 2006; Volet & Wosnitza, 2005).

Furthermore, because emotions are a component of larger, more full human experiences, they cannot be separated from learning settings and experiences (Brookfield, 2006; Lehman, 2006; Plutchick, 2003). Dirx (2008) and Brookfield (2006) also make the argument that emotion is usually seen as a barrier to effective teaching and learning. More complex effects of emotions on learning than just suppressing reason and rational reasoning are likely to exist. Understanding the different sorts of emotions that exist in classrooms and learning environments can help with learning because all human behaviors and thinking require the right emotions to be successful (Barbalet, 2002).

Moreover, the relationship between emotions and learning deserves further study (Damasio, 2003; Dirx, 2008; Dirx & Cranton, 1997; Eich et al., 2000; LeDoux, 1996) since there is no evidence yet linking emotional presence to learning. The issue of how emotions impact students' thinking is still up for debate, as are the various factors that influence students' emotional presence and how those impact learning, particularly in online courses.

Students are gradually warming to the comfort of online classes as the world adjusts to the "New Normal" brought on by the Novel coronavirus (COVID-19). The current situation has spurred innovation in the sphere of education. The usage of computer-based multimedia instructional technology and large-scale open online courses has increased. People have seen innovative strategies, such as take-home materials and radio and television shows, to improve the continuity of education and training (Riley et al., 2022).

Online learning entails either entirely online courses or courses that combine Internet delivery with sporadic in-person encounters (Hong et al., 2021). When instruction is provided in this manner, interaction occurs between the teacher and the students, even when they are physically distant from each other. This implies that the teaching is occurring outside the traditional in-person environment.

In lieu, Angara (2020) discussed the potential enormous impacts of the rapid shift in educational paradigm into the "New Normal" on learners' overall development. One of them is how this new educational model and the way that instruction is delivered will affect the students' mental health and emotional stability. He underlined how the students' emotions will be strained by the lack of technology and internet access. The way technology is used and the fact that they are unable to communicate with their teachers, who are located remotely, frequently irritate

students. These changes to our educational setting have a significant effect on everyone involved in teaching and learning acquisitions, particularly in terms of how the courses are delivered. They also bear the brunt of the repercussions.

The researcher conducted this study as a result of the lack of evidence explaining this concern and the dearth of specific research studies that will demonstrate how students' emotional presence during online lectures affects their learning, particularly at this moment. Nevertheless, this study was conducted to fully comprehend the level of academic achievement of the students in online settings, the emotional presence of the students in an online learning environment, and whether there is a relationship between the emotional presence of the students and their academic achievement in online learning.

Objectives

The purpose of this study was to fully comprehend the relationship that might exist between the emotional presence of the students and their academic achievement in online learning. In particular, this research aimed to address the subsequent questions:

1. To what degree does emotion manifest during the online learning process experienced by the participants?
2. What is the level of academic achievements of the students in online learning?
3. Is there any significant relationship between the Levels of Academic Achievement and the Emotional Presence of the Students in Online Learning?
4. Is there any significant difference between the Levels of Academic Achievement of the Students in Online Learning?

Methodology:

This study employed an exploratory sequential mixed-method design since, according to Majeski et al. (2018), it is the least used method in exploring emotional presence and academic achievement, yet it is viewed as the most suitable methodology to understand the said problem. Furthermore, several scholars also highlighted the need for additional mixed-methods research in this area (Lorensius et al., 2021; Ejiogu et al., 2021; Cailen, 2020; Jacob et al., 2020; and Dwivedi et al., 2020).

Population and Sampling:

Thus, this study was participated by 50 students from the senior high school department of Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., who were selected using the purposive sampling technique (Frost, 2023), following the given criteria: they must be enrolled in online classes and have the same amount of time spent in online learning with the same set of subjects and teachers. The number of males and females is equally distributed throughout the study, with an age range of 16 to 18 years old. These criteria are in response to the recommendations of Jiang & Koo (2020).

Instrumentations:

For the data collection instrument, the researcher made use of the previous grades of the students in the said school year, which were then analyzed. Furthermore, a semi-structured interview was also facilitated to determine the emotional presence of the participants. Records from the homeroom guidance were also used to support or

disagree with the gathered data. The researcher also used a 10-point Likert scale to determine the emotional presence of the students.

Data Collection:

To gather the needed data, the researcher of the study secured a permission letter first from the school administrator of the chosen locale. Then, letters of consent and participation were given to the participants. Before the interview, the participants were provided with information about the study's objectives and the ethical factors that were important to consider.

Data Analysis:

A t-test and Pearson R were used to analyze the relationship and significant difference between the emotional presence of the students (before, during, and after) and their academic achievements. The analytical component of this study is the student. To evaluate the qualitative information obtained from open-ended questions about the online experience, three different codings were employed: open, axial, and selective coding. The researcher discussed the emotional presence found in the textual data after thoroughly reading all of the narratives of the respondents. In phase one, the emotional response was put into different groups based on a list by Cleveland-Innes and Campbell (2012). After analyzing and evaluating, the results of this study became the basis of the new program in the school known as "APeer Tayo".

Ethical Considerations:

Prior to the data gathering, all pertinent letters were secured by the researchers. After the approval, the participant-respondents were oriented regarding the purposes of the study. They were not required to include any identifying information in the survey. Alternatively, comments were kept anonymous for the purposes of this research study. The researcher made every effort to protect the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents, including the following:

1. Assigning code names or numbers to participants that were used on all research notes and documents.
2. Notes, interview transcripts, and any other information that could have been used to identify a participant were kept in a safe place or on a protected drive.
3. Except in cases where the researcher was legally required to report specific incidents, participant's data was kept confidential. These things include, but were not limited to, abuses, abuse of power and the risk of suicide.

The participation of the respondents in this study was voluntary. It was up to them to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If the respondents decided to take part in this study, they were asked to sign a consent form. After they signed the consent form, they were still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study did not affect the relationship the researcher had, if any, with the respondents. If the respondents withdrew from the study before data collection was completed, the data was returned to them or destroyed.

Results and Discussions:

Presented below are the key findings and data analysis gathered from the responses of the 50 SHS respondents.

RQ1: Emotional Presence in Online Learning Experiences

Out of the identified 15 emotional responses of Cleveland-Innes and Campbell (2012), anxious (15 times) and afraid (13 times) appeared frequently in the responses of the participants when asked regarding their online experiences. One participant said that "due to too many activities and deadlines, I tend to feel anxious....." Another participant exclaimed, "I am always afraid during examination week. I don't want to get low grades." And one detailed his/her response:

"There are instances that due to simultaneously activities and performance tasks to be submitted, I am not sleeping on time and forget to take my dinner. I am anxious to finish all the academic stuff and receive low grades."

This emotional presence of the students during online classes is supported by Wang C et al. (2020). He stated that students are more likely to experience worry due to their psychological challenges and conditions in terms of learning. This is because of a combined concern about what to do in school, how to beat deadlines, and communicating with teachers while doing home responsibilities.

Another emotional response observed was disappointment, which appeared 10 times in the responses of the participants. Participants exclaimed that "Every time I lose internet connection and get low grades, I tend to feel disappointed." Another student added that "Sometimes I cannot open the files posted by the teachers and need to go to other places just to have good internet connections, yet it is still hard to do the tasks, which leads to too much disappointment and frustration." Students who did not have devices or a good internet connection performed less well in online classes and were more likely to get bad grades or drop out than their peers from wealthy families (Cleofas, 2021). The data here draws two conclusions, which require further research. First, what is the connection between family status and the occurrence of emotional presence among the students, and how might it affect the academic achievement of the students? Secondly, adverse emotions are typically prompted by unfavorable events that lead to undesirable results.

Frustration and the feeling of irritability also emerged in the responses of the participants 9 times. "Most of the time, though I studied the lessons the whole day, I still got bad grades. This is very frustrating for me since I do not receive bad grades when I am in face-to-face classes."

In contrast to the negative emotional responses of the participants, there were participants who exclaimed positive responses. In fact, happiness, a state of contentment and well-being, appeared 8 times in responses. One participant said, "Attending online classes makes me happy because I was able to see my classmates virtually and was given a chance to converse with them." Another participant said, "The humor of the teachers makes me (the class) happy and excited to attend classes. This makes the discussion light and enjoyable". One participant also mentioned that "Our Theology teacher always show(s) big smiles even though we are learning online. Her happiness is contagious to us." This asserts that connection between the students and teachers during online classes is very significant to effective transfer of learning. Teachers who place value on the emotional quotient of the students tend to develop an amiable and undisturbed learning environment. This also shows that students recognized the efforts of the teachers while doing online lectures.

Excitement, an emotional condition characterized by zeal, desire, or anticipation as well as general arousal (Cleveland-Innes and Campbell 2012), also emerged 7 times in the study. This response was supported by this statement from the participants: "The online games like kahoot, quiz board, and think-talk used by our teachers, especially in research, always make me eager (excited) to attend the class. Sir ***** also gives jokes and punch lines that make the class come alive. "

Furthermore, yearning, a strong feeling of wishing or longing towards something, was found five times. One participant specified, "I hope that the roll-out of the vaccine will be effective and all students will get vaccinated for the government to start implementing face-to-face classes since online classes are not that engaging for me." Another added, "I am already bored attending classes every day. How I wish that all we experience today was just a nightmare. I missed my old life... "

Participants expressed wonder, a need for knowledge inside that waits to be awakened by reality three times. "I'm interested in learning more strategies for improving my learning styles to use in this learning environment."

Lastly is shy, the presence of anxious reactions appeared 2 times. One participant stated that "Though I know the answers during the recitations, I tend not to answer the questions because I am anxious."

Based on the data above, it is clearly observable that the emotional responses of the participants are negative since the most frequently expressed emotional responses were anxious, afraid, disappointment, and frustration, which according to Cleveland-Innes and Campbell (2012) are negative emotional responses.

Table 1. Descriptive Data of Students Emotional Presence in Online Classes

EMERGE OF EMOTION IN ONLINE LEARNING						
Subjects	Before Exam	During Exam	After Exam	Average	Interpretations	Rank
Reading and Writing	7.50	5.48	8.36	7.11	Slightly Okay	6
Pagbasa at Pagsusuri ng Ibat Ibang Teksto	7.72	5.60	8.50	7.27	Slightly Okay	4
Statistics and Probability	7.36	5.42	8.42	7.07	Slightly Okay	7
Physical Science	7.44	4.98	8.12	6.85	Neutral	10
Personal Development/ Pansariling Kaunlaran	7.86	5.44	8.48	7.26	Slightly Okay	5
Physical Education and Health 2	7.68	5.56	8.66	7.30	Slightly Okay	3
Research in Daily Life 1	7.96	5.72	8.68	7.45	Slightly Okay	2
Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences	7.70	5.06	8.32	7.03	Slightly Okay	9
Creative Writing/ Malikhaing Pagsulat	7.56	5.10	8.50	7.05	Slightly Okay	8
Theology 2	8.16	6.30	9.20	7.89	Slightly Okay	1
Average	7.69	5.47	8.52	7.23	Slightly Okay	

After the interview process, the respondents were asked to rate their emotional presence during online classes three times: two weeks before the examination week, during the examination week, and two weeks after the examinations. The assessments were done during the identified weeks when the emotional responses of the respondents were significantly notable. A ten-point Likert scale was employed for the assessment of students' emotional presence.

Table 1 shows that the general emotional presence of the respondents based on the computed average was Slightly Okay (7.69) two weeks before examinations, while Neither Okay Nor Bad (5.47) during examination week, and Moderately Okay (8.52) two weeks after the examination week. Overall, the emotional presence of the respondents before, during, and after examinations is Slightly Okay with a computed average of 7.23.

The information presented indicates that the emotional presence of the participants fluctuates or varies based on the number of tasks they are required to finish within a specific timeframe. For instance, because respondents do not feel the strain of the tasks they must complete, they have a slightly okay emotional presence before the test. On the other hand, the emotional presence of the respondents abruptly changes during the examination week since it is the time that the amount of pressure, for instance, and workloads of the respondents increase. These situations make the emotional presence of the respondents neither okay nor bad. However, after the examination week, the emotional presence of the respondents seemed to become more positive (Zembylas, 2008; Cleveland-Innes and Campbell, 2012). This is because the number of school activities is lower, and the pressure is not as high.

During the examination week of the respondents, it was also notable the number of posts and messages the students shared on various social media sites. Though the occurrence of social media is not presented in the study, the emotional presence expressed there is imperative to consider. Some students expressed their uncertainties and anxiety regarding the results of the examinations. Others posted that almost all of what they reviewed before examinations was not included on the exam. However, after all the examinations, respondents expressed a sigh of relief and a positive outlook. Alalwan (2022) claimed that students' satisfaction with their learning experiences showed a positive connection to their active engagement with various social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and similar platforms.

The data in Table 1 also presents which subjects respondents tend to have good emotional presence, which are Theology 2, Research in Daily Life 1, and Physical Education and Health 2. This data shows that the subject and how the teacher handles the class might affect the emotional presence of the respondents. For instance, in the subject of Theology 2, some respondents mentioned that because their teacher in the subject always shows genuine smiles and happy faces, they tend to have a light and unpressured online learning environment. This data was affirmed by another participant who emphasized the humor of the teachers in the research subject and the various online activities used by the teachers to make their emotional presence good.

However, respondents showed low emotional presence in Physical Science, Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences, and Creative Writing/Malikhaing Pagsulat. This can be supported by one of the statements of the respondents asserting that "Some concepts can be challenging to grasp, such as those found in physical science. The difficulty arises from the need to navigate various forms of information simultaneously, including experiments, formulas, calculations, graphs, and conceptual explanations."

RQ2: Level of Academic Achievements of the Students in Online Learning

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Academic Achievements of Students in Online Learning

LEVELS OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT					
Subjects	Computed Grades				
	Before	During	After	Average	Rank
Reading and Writing	87.10	87.66	90.76	88.51	10
Pagbasa at Pagsusuri ng Ibat Ibang Teksto Tungo sa Pananaliksik	89.92	89.84	91.16	90.31	3
Statistics and Probability	89.62	88.40	90.98	89.67	7
Physical Science	87.34	88.82	90.62	88.93	9
Personal Development/ Pansariling Kaunlaran	87.96	90.12	91.44	89.84	6
Physical Education and Health 2	89.22	89.68	90.88	89.93	5
Research in Daily Life 1	88.02	89.88	92.14	90.01	4
Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences	90.60	91.40	93.00	91.67	1
Creative Writing/ Malikhaing Pagsulat	88.48	88.36	91.58	89.47	8
Theology 2	90.68	91.24	91.36	91.09	2
Average	88.89	89.54	91.39	89.94	

The academic achievements of the respondents were assessed three times; two weeks before the examination week, during the examination week, and two weeks after the examination week. The assessments were done by computing the initial grades of the respondents before the examination, after the results of the examinations, and after a new set of activities were given after the examinations.

Based on the computed grades of the respondents, Table 2 shows that before the examination, respondents got an average grade of 88.89, which is Very Satisfactory. Then, after the results of the examination were added, the respondents got an average grade of 89.54, which is Very Satisfactory as well. Two weeks after the examinations and a new set of activities were added, respondents now got an average of 91.39 grades with an Outstanding remark. Overall, the computed general average of the respondents at the time when the study was tested was 89.94, Very Satisfactory. This shows that the students can still get good grades despite the negative emotional presence (Jiang & Koo, 2020).

Table 2 also reveals the subjects in which respondents did well. It is significant to note that the subject where respondents got the highest average was Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences, in which the emotional presence of the respondents was low or negative. This is followed by Theology 2 and Pagbasa’t Pagsusuri ng Ibat Ibang Teksto Tungo sa Pananaliksik. The subjects where the respondents got the lowest average were Reading and Writing, Physical Science, and Creative Writing/Malikhaing Pagsulat. Supervía and Salavera (2019) claimed that a strong correlation exists between school performance, academic engagement, and emotional intelligence. This interconnectedness, in turn, serves as a predictor for one’s commitment to academic responsibilities. Moreover, Vatansever (2022) highlighted that despite students harboring adverse emotions toward specific subjects, maintaining a positive teacher-student relationship can still lead to favorable academic outcomes.

RQ3: Significant Relationship between the Levels of Academic Achievement and the Emotional Response of the Students in Online Learning

Table 3. Relationship of the Emotional Presence (XX) and Academic Achievements (YY) of the Respondents

Emotional Presence and Academic Achievements				
Variables	df	p- value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
XX and YY	10	0.180	Accept	Not Significant

Using the Pearson correlation coefficient, the null hypothesis is accepted as the calculated p-value (0.180) is higher than the critical value of 0.05. This indicates that the level of emotional presence exhibited by the participants does not have a noteworthy correlation with their academic performance.

This finding debunked a lot of existing literature, such as the findings of Cottrell (2005), Baumeister, DeWall, and Zhang (2007), Derks et al. (2008), and Cleveland-Innes and Campbell (2012), which asserted that feelings have an impact on results. In other words, positive emotions bring about positive things, whereas negative emotions bring about negative things. Additionally, it also contradicted the findings of Baumeister et al. (2007), which concluded that negative emotions like stress and rage might hinder performance. Negative emotions, such as rage and shame, have been shown to affect judgment and cause people to take unwise risks. As well as the findings of Dirx (2008) and Brookfield (2006), stating that negative emotions are usually seen as a barrier to effective teaching and learning while positive emotions promote better learning.

For instance, in Table 2, respondents got the highest average grade of 91.67 in Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences, despite the fact that it is second to the last subject with low or negative emotional presence (Table 1). This implies that emotional presence exhibits no statistically significant correlation with the academic performance of the participants.

Table 4. Comparative Assessments of Emotional Presence (Before, During, After) and Academic Achievement (Before, During, After)

Variables	p- value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
AAB – EPB	0.310	Accept	Not Significant
AAD – EPD	0.286	Accept	Not Significant
AAA – EPA	0.82	Accept	Not Significant

a=0.05

Table 4 shows that when the emotional presence (EP) is directly compared to the academic achievements (AA) of the respondents (0.310, 0.286, and 0.82), the decision for Null is Accepted since the computed p-value is higher than the critical value of 0.05. This means that emotional presence has no significant relationship to the academic achievement of the students. The connection between employing emotions to enhance thinking and academic achievement is minimal, while the comprehension and regulation of emotions are undeniably associated with scholastic success, particularly when it comes to emotional understanding, which exhibits the most robust correlation (Costa and Faria, 2020, Romano et al., 2020).

RQ4: Significant difference between the Levels of Academic Achievement of the Students in Online Learning

Table 5. Levels of Academic Achievement of the Students in Online Learning

Variables	computed t	p- value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
AC-B	216.1	0.000	Rejected	Significant
AC-D	229.9	0.000	Rejected	Significant
AC-A	401.4	0.000	Rejected	Significant

Table 5 shows that the t-test result indicates a rejection of the Null hypothesis of the study (0.000, 0.000, and 0.000) since the computed p-value is lower than the critical value of 0.05. This entails a notable variance in student academic performance across the periods preceding, concurrent with, and after examinations. Students who have more working hours have less time for them self to spend on recreational activities, relaxation, and sleep may result in being unable to receive good grades (Kumar, 2020).

Conclusions:

The existence of an emotional presence in online learning is crucial since emotions may hinder or support the transfer of learning. And, as our educational system begins to embrace the use of online learning, it is critical to conduct a thorough examination of it.

In this exploratory sequential mixed-methods paper, the emotional presence and academic achievements of the students were analyzed. The analyses were done three times (before, during, and after examinations) in the weeks when the emotional presence of the students was unsteady. The first phase of analysis is a thematic analysis in which, based on the responses of the participants, most of the identified emotional presence is negative (anxious, afraid, and disappointed). This was supported by the gathered data in Table 1, which shows that the general emotional presence of the respondents is only slightly okay. Thus, despite the fact that the emotional presence of the respondents is only slightly okay, the data shows that the students still obtain very satisfactory remarks on their academic achievements. This concludes that even though the students encountered low and negative emotional presence, they could still achieve satisfactory grades, and vice versa. The findings also show that the emotional presence of the respondents in the identified weeks of unsteady emotions has no significant relationship to their academic achievements. This suggests that students' emotional presence is not a strong predictor of their academic success in online classes. Emotional presence in this sense might exist on a separate level.

Moreover, qualitative analysis of the data also showed that the rapport of the teachers with the students might affect their emotional presence and acquisition of learning. Teachers who considered students' emotions during online classes received positive remarks from the students and were able to build a strong online learning environment. In addition, it was also discovered that social media is the main outlet for students to express their emotions. And this aspect should be considered by both the school and other researchers. Quantitative data, on the other hand, showed that students might get good grades in subjects where the emotional presence is low or negative.

Furthermore, even though emotional presence is not significantly correlated with students' academic achievements in online learning, teachers and educational institutions should still place value and importance on students' emotional presence. Since emotional presence, according to other existing literature, is important to the academic achievements of the students, this fact must be taken into account as either a major component of learning—both online and offline—or at the very least as a pervasive, influential component.

Recommendations:

Emotions cannot be separated from learning settings, whether they be face-to-face or online, since they are a component of the deeper, more complete human experience. Despite the fact that this subject has typically been disregarded in educational research, the relationship between emotion and learning has recently drawn increasing attention. The present study is one of the recent steps towards the analysis of the emotional presence and academic achievement of students in an online learning environment. Despite the fact that the findings of this study contradict much of the existing literature in these fields, a broad range of conclusions should be drawn from them.

Future researchers and educators should recognize and understand the magnitude of emotions and emotional presence in an online learning environment in a larger population since the present study dealt only with 50 senior high school students at one private institution. And, if possible, in various types of online learning environments, such as hybrid courses. The emotional presence of students in public school settings might also be considered in future studies of the same variables. Testing or piloting a more valid instrument is also subject to reconsideration since the data from the qualitative analysis is quite different from the data in the quantitative part. Though the instruments used in this study were validated by a registered psychometrician, it is still advisable to get a more valid test that will measure the emotional presence of the students. Others might also consider the different factors that affect the emotional presence of students in an online learning environment.

When it comes to classroom practices, teachers, as facilitators and mediators of learning, should create an online learning environment that fosters students' emotional and educational needs. They may also practice a simple "Kumustahan" session, which will serve as the students' break from academic work. Finding out what online learners need and how teachers can create a productive and collaborative learning community are important steps to take. In addition, since the learners of today are said to be digital natives, the integration of new online applications such as Kahoot, SlideDeck, Slido, and others should be taken into account.

Our institution, Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., as the key partner of the results of this study and other research papers, have done either within our locale or outside, is on its way toward the implementation of a more feasible, emotional-responsive, and data-driven program, such as the "aPeer Tayo." This term is inspired and adapted from the Filipino word "Apir Tayo", which means giving a positive vibe, such as support. The program is currently in the implementation phase and will soon be evaluated. The school created this despite the fact that emotional presence has no relationship to academic achievements but because of the narratives of the students.

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